

Research

Influence of Project Management Factors on Building Performance in Lagos State of Nigeria

**Odukoya¹, Abdul Jubreel Babatunde, Azmin², Adi Anuar, Ibrahim³ Fazdliel
Aswad & Sakdan⁴, Mohd. Fo'ad**

¹Faculty of Business & Communication, Universiti Malaysia Perlis (UniMAP), Perlis, Malaysia
Tel: +60-16-430-3267 / +1-929-677-9563 Email: tundeodukoya@yahoo.com

²Faculty of Business & Communication, Universiti Malaysia Perlis (UniMAP), Perlis, Malaysia
Tel: +6019-448-5074 Email: adianuar@unimap.edu.my

³Faculty of Civil Engineering & Technology, Universiti Malaysia Perlis (UniMAP), Perlis, Malaysia
Tel: +6019-346--7064 Email: fazdliel@unimap.edu.my

⁴Professor & Deputy Vice Chancellor, Students Affairs & Alumni, Universiti Malaysia Perlis (UniMAP), Perlis, Malaysia
Tel: +60-19-456-1666 Email: mfs@unimap.edu.my

Abstract: This paper examines the influence of Project Management Factors on Building Performances in Lagos State of Nigeria. The study specifically investigated the relationship and influence of Project Management Factors (Project Manager and Team Competencies, Project Related Factors and Project Technicality). The survey research design was employed in this study. A well-structured questionnaire was administered on the respondents and used to elicit information on the relationship and influence of Project Manager and Team Members' Competency, Project Related Factors and Building Performance and Project Technicality (PT) on Building Performance. Data was collected from building construction professionals which includes Nigerian Institute Builders, Nigerian Institute of Civil Engineers, Nigerian Institute of Quantity Surveyors and Nigerian Institute of Town Planners. A total of 367 samples were selected from the study population using the stratified sampling technique. Correlation and regression analysis were used to summarize the findings. The study found that there is a significant relationship between the Project Management Factors and Building Performance. Furthermore, the study found that Project Management Factors: Project Manager and Team Members' Competency ($t=9.546, p<.05$), Project Related Factors ($t=4.506, p<.05$) and Project Technicality ($t=5.722, p<.05$) influence Building Performance in Lagos State of Nigeria. Based on the results, the study recommends a critical project management approach in building construction while putting all the factors into considerations, and that Government agency involved in building construction should ensure all safety guidelines are strictly adhered.

Keywords: Project Management Factors, Building Performance, Project Technicality, Competency, Project Related Factors

*Corresponding Author: Odukoya, Abdul Jubreel Babatunde

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Introduction

Sustained development remains a vital goal of every society of which building structures play significant role. This is also true of both the Global North and South. Building construction all over the world constitutes one of the most treasured assets of human-kind. It provides accommodation for diverse purposes to mankind. In addition to the importance that buildings provide people with abundant accommodation such as offices, houses, schools, mosques, churches, hospitals etc. They also provide employment to trained and untrained people (Oyedele et al., 2015; Zaki, et al., 2019).

Building construction industry provides structures that improve/enhance quality of life, generates employment, contribute to Gross National Product (GNP) and Gross Domestic Product (GDP). These structures help to enhance the quality of life, generate employment, contributes to Gross National Product (GNP) and Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in every country (Ali, Shahir & Bin, 2014). However, construction industry performance is poor. Especially, poor building performance has continued to threaten its importance to human-kind. Poor building performance results to building failure and collapse. Building construction collapses are not new occurrences in the building industry globally but what is disturbing is the rate at which structures totally collapse or fail in the developing countries (Akinjare, et al., 2021). Study has shown that the incidences of building collapse or failure constitutes a foremost source of concern to all professionals, stakeholders and governments in the building industry around the world.

In continuation, human and material wastes associated with such building collapse and psychological wounds often inflicted on residents of such houses and their owners also constitute huge losses. Statutory building development practices in Nigeria and countries all over the world is guided by regulations and laws through parliament enactment and procedures that are to be administered by specific government agencies and construction professionals. However, these laws, enactments and procedures are often threatened, altered or neglected leading to substandard malpractices in building construction (Truman & King, 2018; Akinjare, et al., 2021).

Truman and King (2018) were of the opinion that one of the major factors affecting building performance is poor construction project management. Project management objectives are to be achieved by project managers. This is done through applying and integrating project management factors to different aspect of the project towards its success. Richman (2011) defined project management in terms of having a project that is successfully completed. According to him, project management entails actions that guarantee that projects are completed in accordance with set time, budget, and scope objectives. To put it more simply, according to ISO 21500 (2013) definition, project management is applying methods, tools, techniques, and competencies to a project in order to ensure its success. Observations show that the construction companies have been working on different several projects which have increased drastically over the last two decades. The increase calls for implementation on project management methods and tools to become successful and sustainable. Truman and King (2018) identified project management factors as a concept that includes project manager and team member's competency and project related factors. According to Spalek (2014) the success of building

projects relies heavily on three major factors which are: project related factors, people in project (project manager and team) and organizational contexts.

Studies have shown that there have been poor performances of building in Lagos Nigeria lately. For instance, Oloke, Ogunde and Joshua (2017) revealed that building collapse in Nigeria and Lagos specifically has been on the increase. Ayodeji et al., (2017) attributed this menace to the insensitivity of property owners in the bid to save cost without knowing what this will cost them. Oloke, Ogunde and Joshua (2017) on the other hand believed that poor project management caused by project manager and team members' incompetency and inefficient project related factors are some of the major problems affecting the poor building performance and collapse in Lagos. Hence, a motivation for this research which is to examine the influence of project management factors on building performances and specifically to investigate the influence of project related factors and project manager and team competencies on building performance in Lagos State Nigeria.

Conceptual Review: Project Management

The term project management has no universally accepted definition. The goals of project management have, however, been sought to conceptualize in some excellent definitions. Project management, according to the Project Management Institute (2013), is the process of applying information, skills, tools, and techniques to project operations in order to achieve project requirements. According to the International Project Management Association (2006), project management is an organized process with time and financial constraints that is designed to accomplish a specific project goal. The planning, execution, and monitoring of project operations to achieve project objectives are collectively referred to as project management. This is done by successfully managing and balancing the limitations of scope, time, and money (Peng et al., 2007). The process of applying information, skills, tools, and procedures to project activities in order to achieve project requirements is known as project management. In other words, it is a series of planned actions taken to fulfill a particular objective. The transition from input to output is the core of project management and necessitates integration and iteration. These processes control the inputs to and product outputs from certain activities.

The term Project Management Factors originated from the US defense aerospace in 1953 as critical and well recognized issues in construction industry (Sanjuan & Froese, 2013). The goal of project management is to initiate, plan, execute, monitor, control, and close a project in order to efficiently and successfully accomplish the desired aim. The use and integration of project management factors, together with the Project Manager and Team Members' shared accountability for accomplishing project objectives, are additional methods for attaining project management objectives. Within the scope of this study, project management factors include Project Manager and Team Member Competency (PMTMC), Project Related Factors (PRF) which include project planning, coordination, communication etc and project technicality which is characterized of project tools, technological knowhow and methods.

Building Performance

The term building performance is derived from the various tentacles of the word performance. According to Chendo and Obi (2015), building performance refers to the physical performance of a building as a whole or in its component elements. This refers to a building's capacity to contribute to carrying out the tasks associated with its intended purpose. Additionally, how a building's users interact with its physical surroundings, work conditions, and neighboring businesses can affect how well it performs (Mahamid, 2016). User requirements and a methodical evaluation of a predicted or actual performance over the full building life/cycle are two aspects of the performance approach (Gargate & Momaya, 2018). Building officers must set goals that are motivated by comfort, safety, health, and other factors in order to measure the performance of buildings. Traditionally, the term 'Building Performance' has been used in the framework of indoor

air quality, fire safety, thermal efficiency and noise control. Each of these “micro-level” criteria are important to facilitate understanding on how well the building is fulfilling its functional requirements (De Wilde, 2019; Jin, et al., 2019). However, to assess how well structured or the quality of a building is in the long term, a holistic approach is needed for a total building performance.

Moreso, total Building Performance is currently taking a higher profile, and this can be attributed to the following reasons. Firstly, the expectations and requirements of building users have increased due to advances in technology and also changes in economic conditions (De Wilde, 2019). People demand more from the buildings thus resulting in the increased expectations of building performance (Adamy& Abu Bakar, 2021).

Project Management Factors and Building Performance

Dziekoński (2017) posits that success or performance of every project depends on the effort of Project Manager and Team Members who carry out the whole construction project activities. Project Managers and Team Members are critical to the success and performance of every project. Thus, they influence performance of construction projects. Elzomor& Parrish (2016) posits that Project Manager and Team Members’ Factors have important elements (Skills, knowledge, experience, abilities & selection) of the right team members who are technologically competent and understand the organization and its business requirements. Ifediora, Egolum, & Emoh (2019) assert that Project Team Member and Managers’ Competency is very important as it influences project scheduling, planning and communication which culminate to building performance. Hence this study hypothesizes that there is a significant effect of Project Manager and Team Members’ Competency (PMTMC) on Building Performance (BPM). Project Related Factors (PRF) plays an important role to ensure the successful implementation of Building performances (BPM) (Hornstein, 2015).

Project Related Factors (PRF) are the key to the management success. Venczel, Berényi, & Hriczó (2021) suggests that by using the project related tools such as initiating process, effort monitoring, control mechanism effectiveness, communication system effectiveness, coordination effectiveness, decision making effectiveness, effective quality assurance program, formal dispute resolution process, incentives on every successful construction project and delivery handover system, the project managers would be able to plan and execute their building projects to maximize the project’s chances of success (Venczel, Berényi, & Hriczó, 2021).

Conceptual Framework

This conceptual framework that used in this study explains the interaction and influence of Project Management Factors on Building Performance. Project Management Factors within the context of this study includes: Project Manager and Team Member Competency, Project Related Factors (planning, monitoring, communication system, decision making, quality assurance, dispute resolution etc.) and Project Technicality (tools and methods). The conceptual framework is a Venn diagram that explains the interaction between the independent variable (project management factors) and the dependent variable (building performance).

Project Management Factors and Building Performance

Methodology

The survey research design was employed in this study. A well-structured questionnaire was employed as a tool in conducting the survey. The questionnaire was used to elicit information on: the relationship and influence of Project Manager and Team Members’ Competency (PMTMC), Project Related Factors (PRF) and Building Performance (BPM) and Project Technicality (PT) on Building Performance. Questionnaire is most appropriate for this study because the number of professionals that would serve as respondents is large. The unit analysis of this study were professionals from the Nigerian Institute of Builders, Lagos State branch, Nigerian Institute of Civil Engineers, Lagos State branch, Nigerian Institute of Quantity Surveyors, Lagos State branch, and Nigerian Institute of Town Planners, Lagos State branch. Data were therefore collected from building construction professionals which includes Nigerian Institute Builders, Nigerian Institute of Civil Engineers, Nigerian Institute of Quantity Surveyors and Nigerian Institute of Town Planners. A total of 367 sample were selected from the study population using the stratified sampling technique. The strata used were categorized as Builders, Civil Engineers, Quantity Surveyors, and Town Planners. Data obtained were analyzed using inferential statistics. Correlation and regression analysis were used to summarize the findings.

Results

Table 1: Correlation Summary Table

Variable	r	P
Project Manager and Team Members’ Competency	.314	.007
Project Related Factors	.218	.014
Project Technicality	.264	.003

Dependent Variable: Building Performance

Result presented in Table 1 reveals that there is a significant relationship between project manager and team member’s competency ($r=.314, p<.05$), project related factors ($r=.218, p<.05$), project technicality ($r=.264, p<.05$) and building performance.

Table 2: Regression Summary Table

Variable	Beta	Std. Error	t	p
Project Manager and Team Members' Competency	0.38	0.041	9.546	.007
Project Related Factors	0.245	0.054	4.506	.014
Project Technicality	0.291	0.049	5.722	.003

Dependent Variable: Building Performance

Result presented in Table 2 on the influence of Project Management Factors on Building Performance revealed that Project Manager and Team Members' Competency ($t=9.546$, $p<.05$), Project Related Factors ($t=4.506$, $p<.05$) and Project Technicality ($t=5.722$, $p<.05$) has a significant influence on Building Performance. In addition, it is evident that 1 unit increase in Project Manager Team Member's Competency results in 0.38 unit increase in Building Performance, likewise a unit increase in Project Related Factors results in 0.245 increase in Building Performance while a unit increase in Project Technicality accounts for 0.291 increase in Building Performance. From the foregoing, the Project Management Factors are significant predictors of Building Performance while Project Manager Team Members' Competency has the most influence. This is in tandem with Dziekonski (2017) who was of the opinion that performance of every project has a lot to do with the efforts and expertise of Project Management Team Members who are involved in carrying out the construction projects. Furthermore, the study confirms the findings of Elzomor and Parrish (2016) that highlighted the importance of skills, knowledge, experience and ability of the Project Manager and Team Members to understand the project requirements. Venczel, Berenyi and Hriczo (2021) suggest that Project Related Factors and Technicality such as communication effectiveness, coordination and decision-making effectiveness, technological knowhow, hardware and software cannot be excluded from achieving a required Building Performance.

Concluding Remarks

This study examined the influence of Project Management Factors on Building Performance in Lagos State of Nigeria. Over the last few years, there has been continuous increase the number of degrading building performance in building constructions that has led to increasing records in constructed buildings in Lagos State of Nigeria. A significant relationship exists between the Project Management Factors and Building Performance. It was also discovered that Project Management Factors: Project Manager and Team Members' Competency, Project Related Factors and Project Technicality Influences Building Performance in Lagos State of Nigeria. The implication is that the Project Management Factors have not been sustainably coordinated for most of the collapsed building in Lagos State. The study therefore recommends a critical project management approach in building construction while putting all the factors into considerations, and that Government agency involved in building construction should ensure all safety guidelines are strictly adhered.

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The Corresponding Author: Odukoya, Abdul Jubreel Babatunde was a postgraduate researcher with the faculty of Applied & Human Sciences, Universiti Malaysia Perlis (UniMAP), Perlis, Malaysia

